

RELATIONSHIP OF THINKING AND IMAGINATION PROCESSES WITH SPEECH
ACTIVITY

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Resume. In recent years, many studies have begun to appear in world psychology and linguistics on issues of the psyche, language, and speech activity. Because the bulk of information reaches human consciousness through the linguistic direction. The article describes the relationship between the processes of thinking and imagination in the field of psycholinguistics and speech activity. And their research is expressed based on scientific sources. It studies language and perception, thinking, and the “nature of language.” In the real mental activity of a person, a mental process, state or characteristic of a person is manifested.

At the same time, the processes of thinking, perception and imagination are expressed in speech activity. The article indicates that the direction of psycholinguistics is important in the study and disclosure of these issues.

Key words: perception, thinking, imagination, psyche, need, image, speech, language, code, symbol.

СВЯЗЬ ПРОЦЕССОВ МЫШЛЕНИЯ И ВООБРАЖЕНИЯ С РЕЧЕВОЙ
ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬЮ

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Аннотация. В последние годы в мировой психологии и лингвистике стало появляться много исследований, посвященных вопросам психики и языка, речевой деятельности. Потому что основная часть информации доходит до человеческого сознания через лингвистическое направление.

В статье описывается взаимосвязь процессов мышления и воображения в области психолингвистики и речевой деятельности. И их исследования выражены на основе научных источников.

В ней изучаются язык и восприятие, мышление, «природа языка». В реальной психической деятельности человека проявляется психический процесс, состояние или характеристика человека.

При этом в речевой деятельности выражаются процессы мышления, восприятия и воображения. В статье указывается, что направление психолингвистики имеет важное значение в исследовании и раскрытии этих вопросов.

Ключевые слова: восприятие, мышление, воображение, психика, потребность, образ, речь, язык, код, символ.

Enter. Currently, it is important to study the functioning of speech and language units in the conversation process. Also, attention is paid to researching national language characteristics from a scientific point of view. [1.212].

The emergence of speech significantly restructures the entire mental sphere of a person. It is especially important that it is formed in relation to the social environment and surrounding children from birth.

Processes such as perception, memory, thinking, imagination, voluntary attention are formed and mediated in a person only with the participation of speech. This speech, acting as the highest, mental function that is most important for a person, organizes and connects all other mental processes. Speech, which leads to the reconstruction of all qualitative features of thinking, memory and other mental functions, becomes a universal means of influencing the outside world.

The processes of thought and imagination in the human mind are closely related to the activity of speech and constitute a unique human type of mental activity - verbal thinking. The development of speech is closely related to other mental processes. So, speech is included in the process of perception, generalizes and differentiates it. Verbalization of the memorized material (identification of visual-sensual images through appropriate words-definitions, words-concepts) helps memorization and repetition to be meaningful. Also, the role of speech in regulating one's behavior, organizing and developing attention functions is extremely important.

Analysis of literature on the topic. Psyche, E.G. Goziev defines it, is a systematic property (property) of highly organized matter, an active reflection of the objective existence by the subject, the representation of the scenes of this existence without the subject distancing himself from himself, and at the same time, personal control of his behavior and activities. In the psyche, the events of the past, present and future are expressed and organized. Past events are embodied in human memory and are manifested in personal experiences. The present is expressed in a complex of mental processes, emotional experiences, images and imaginations. And the future is reflected in impulses, goals, good intentions, as well as fantasy, pangs of conscience, dreams and dreams [8.21].

Psyche language "manifests itself" even in signs. Characters act as substitutes for images of objects and their relationships. The sign itself (more precisely, the indicator, the sound complex) does not contain any information about reality (ideal or materiality). Signs are a conditional substitute for images. Characters refer only to images and their relationships [6.119]. Each "word" refers to the concept of a "character ordered as a sequence of sounds" created in human life experience and encoded in memory in a complex figurative form. For example, as a sequence of sounds d i v a n, the sign and word "divan" are formed. But information about the structure of the "sofa" will depend on the manifestation of perception, imagination, memory in an figurative form. In this, in the personal experience of a person, his information about the shape of the sofa, the number of legs, height, types and other features is considered important. If this information is not complete enough, or if there is an error, these shortcomings are conspicuous in the person's speech. Errors are observed in the fact that the word can be used and expressed appropriately. Because the use, writing, statement of the word "divan" will depend on how correctly, fully mastered this subject is.

It is difficult to say that words that do not have a complete and correct idea do not occur in everyday life. Because development, progress is the basis for the creation, reproduction of new words.

Economic, socio-political, cultural and technical changes in society are leading to a sharp increase in the number of words entering our national language, that is, the Uzbek language, and a slight change in the essence of meaning [1.212].

Words, concepts, especially related to professional activities, are increasing day by day. The increasing number of inventions, discoveries, types of activities causes the emergence of new words. There will be a variety of ways in which these words are fully, correctly mastered by experts. The role of personal and mental qualities is also important in it. Because the human psyche "manifests itself" in the expression of some kind of images. Images are directly or indirectly related to "original" copies of objects from surrounding reality. Images somehow reflect the characteristics and relationships inherent in these objects.

Research methodology. Currently, L.P.Fedorenko, D.Miller, E.Galanter, E.F.Tarasov, T.N.A number of scientists, such as Ushakova, agree that knowledge is encoded behind the meaning of words and predicative relations" semantic networks "in the form of" numbers", and not in the linguistic form of linguistic signs [7.141].

It is observed that certain functional types of language use become secondary - colloquial in the ratio of the initial and primary form. The study of colloquial speech is very important, since "oral speech is only the norm for assessing the actual language and other forms of speech," indicates the French linguist Sh.Balli [4.24]. And these rules serve as a methodological basis for scientific research.

Analysis and results. Usually, a person uses the listed three forms of coding information about what is indicated in speech statements in his speech activity: psyche, language, activity.

Speaking about the relationship between the psyche and language, it should be remembered that language is primarily a means of activity (speech and mental), the task of which is to satisfy the needs of the individual (vital and spiritual). The task of the language as one of the means of activity is to comprehensively (along with other means) contribute to the implementation of these needs.

The human psyche manifests itself in the expression of any images. Images will be associated directly or indirectly with "original" copies in the surrounding reality of objects. Images somehow reflect the characteristics and relationships inherent in these objects.

Psychic activity uses language only at a certain, most "important" stage (or stages) of its implementation. Including:

1) speech activity is at the stage of the emergence of the need, intention, concept of the sentence. For example, we tell ourselves: "in joy, of course, you need to have a snack", "we need to go to a lecture", "let's talk about the main thing", "prove it", "about ... talk about " and so on.

2) at the stage of afferent synthesis (i.e., analysis of the situation in which activity occurs). For example, before starting a performance, we often tell ourselves: "don't worry, the audience really wants to listen to you. The acoustic properties of the room are conducive to the perception of speech, " etc;

3) at the decision-making stage. We, for example, according to the state of activity, say to ourselves: " I speak (or: I do not speak)"; " I speak Uzbek, Russian, English (or other) language"; " I speak fast (or slow), lip (or extended)", etc.;

4) at the stage of planning activities. For example, when we say to ourselves: "it is better to go out of the Oybek Metro to go to The Art Museum in Tashkent";

5) at the implementation stage. I say to myself (see previous example): "I leave the Oybek metro, turn right along the corridor, near the trees".

At this stage, speech can also be used in the current control process. In this case, certain actions, operas and results of the activity are compared with the prepared plan. Appropriate adjustments are sometimes made to the execution (if necessary) of all movements and operas. For example, we say to ourselves: "No, I made a mistake, I should not have moved to the other side of the Oybek Metro. We have to go back to the other side;

6) at the stage of comparing the results of the completed activity with the goal. For example: "finally, the art museum!"

The nature of the relationship between the psyche and language is determined by many factors. The structure of the individual (in particular, personal needs), the features of mental processes and states, the specifics of the activity or is carried out in speech activity. The level of formation of the mental activity of the individual itself is directly related to the level of formation, as well as the level of formation of linguistic abilities.

Conclusions and suggestions.

Speech is an application of language in practice; it is a language in motion and manifests as a sequence of communication tools at the moment of application.

When conscious communication is carried out to convey a thought and emotion, it assumes the use of means accordingly. At all times, human speech continues to arise from the need for communication in the labor process.

Thus, when considering the relationship of "psyche" and "language", one should not forget that the psyche is an inseparable existence with mutual language. In the Real psychic activity of an individual, one or another psychic process, the state or feature of an individual comes to the fore only temporarily. At the same time, one should not forget about the inseparable connection of mental and emotional in mental activity. Therefore, taking into account special personal relationships in the general system of relations "psyche" - "language (speech)", it is better to remember that this is done primarily for didactic purposes.

LIST OF BIBLIOGRAPHY:

1. Akhmedova M.X. Psycholinguistic features of nonadabic words in youth communication // self-messages, 2021. 1/6. S.212.
2. Akhmedova M., Shodieva N., Rachmanova N. Internal speech in intellectual activity // Academic research in educational sciences. TMA Conference. 2023. 4. 403-407.
3. Akhmedova M.X. The impact of community development on language change // scientific research and innovation. March 2023.2-Vol. No. 2. S. 21-26.
4. Bally Sh. French stylistics. - M.: Publishing House of Foreign Literature, 2001.-C.24.
5. Belyanin V.P. Psycholinguistics. M.2013.
6. Markova A.K. Psychology of language acquisition as a means of communication. – M., 2004.
7. Kovshikov V. A., Pukhov V. P. Psycholinguistics. Theory of speech activity M., 1996. S. 141.
8. Goziev E.G'. General psychology Volume 1. Tashkent. 2004. S. 21.
9. Akhmedova M.X. The impact of social processes on 0 'changes in language // materials of the Republican scientific and practical conference "Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur's role and significance in the development of World Science, Culture". - Scientific publication. - Fergana: FarDU, 2023. S.770-773.
10. Khadimatovna A.M. Spirituality of youth in speech activity // *Academicia: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*. 2021. 11. 10. P.1077-1080.